

Searching For a Philips Curve for Bangladesh: An Econometrics Analysis

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Abstract

The focus of the paper is on the determination of inflation within the framework of Phillips Curve and to investigate whether there exists any relationship between this two. This paper has provided an empirical evidence to support the existence of the Phillips curve in the case of Bangladesh. A linear form of the Phillips curve is estimated using ordinary least squares estimation (OLS). The cointegration test shows long run relation between the variables. This contradicts the theory that in long run the Phillips Curve should be vertical. The important finding is that inflation dynamics in Bangladesh is strongly backward looking. The sample covers annual data from 1972/73 to 2008/09. In order to increase the reliability of the study, we have employed modern time series econometric techniques and procedures.

Keywords: Phillips curve, output gap, potential GDP, cointegration, Granger Causality.

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1. Introduction

In economics, the Phillips curve is a historical inverse relation between the rate of unemployment and the rate of inflation in an economy. Fisher (1926) did the very first investigation in this area. Researchers soon modified the Phillips curve theory and encouraged the development of the expectations-augmented Phillips curve. According to this version, inflation is determined by unemployment gap-the difference between actual unemployment rate and its long-run equilibrium and by the expected inflation¹.

With this expectations augmented Phillips curve, the economy is characterized by a natural rate of unemployment, to which it eventually returns lagged following a shock. "In empirical estimation of the Phillips curve, expected inflation is generally proxied by inflation". (See Ball L. 2008) Researchers have found the existence of expectations-augmented Phillips curve which is also known as NKPC (New Keynesian Phillips Curve), and developed this model further, by suggesting that such a trade-off is not permanent and that in the long-run Phillips curve is vertical.

This paper presents the estimation of the Phillips curve in Bangladesh in details that is suitable to form the basis of a small-scale structural model for the country. The first key issue under investigation is the size of the autoregressive lag coefficient of inflation. This coefficient indicates

¹ In the absence of unemployment gap, output gap model is suggested

whether the rate of inflation in Bangladesh is strongly determined by its own lag values - i.e. whether the Phillips curve is 'backward-looking', or whether it has a forward-looking behavior.

The modeling approach used in ongoing paper has to be justified by the properties of the Bangladesh labor market and given the data constraint. We also estimate the size of the coefficients as represented by the output gap, and the open economy effect measured in import price inflation and in exchange rate.

In general, the inconsistency of data for Bangladesh poses a challenge to the general-to-specific estimation approach of modeling used in this paper. Nevertheless, given the length of the time series a parsimonious linear model of the Phillips curve can still be found for Bangladesh.

The methodological approach, the estimation results, discussed above are presented in this paper as follows. After the introduction, section 2 briefly reviews the existing literature on inflation and unemployment. Section 3 describes the data while section 4 is devoted to inflation modeling strategy. Section 5 shows the results from estimating the traditional Phillips curve showing unit root, cointegration tests as well and finally the Q-SUM test and section 6 then concludes.

2. Literature Survey

Most of the early work on inflation specially by the Policy Analysis Unit of Central Bank, PAU, was done on searching for the determination of inflation based on demand pull and cost push inflation (supply side). As for example, Majumder M.A (2006) discussed inflation from supply side perspectives relating inflation with (labor) cost and import price where it was found that both cost and import price shows significant correlation with (food) inflation. Another paper published by Mujeri Mustafa K (2008) analyzed some important characteristics of inflationary pressure and its impact on various population groups in narrative approach not in econometrics approach and found that the trade off between inflation and growth is somewhat unstable. Basher S. A. and Khan. S. F. (2008) discussed inflation through AD-AS model applying no econometrical approach. Rahman and Younus (2008) discussed some forecasting techniques on inflation by Box-Jenkins's Auto-regressive Integrated Moving Average model, unrestricted Vector Autoregression model and Hsiao's Final Prediction Error criteria. However, the time length was 1990:1-2006:4. For time series analysis, this is after all not long enough. A notable work on inflation done by Khanam R. and Rahman M. M (1995) was based on multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity, autocorrelation. Another work done by Hossain (1996) was on inflation and money supply that examined the causal relationship between this two. Here also unemployment was not the concern.

Akhtaruzzaman Md. studied inflation using co-integration and Vector Error Correction Modeling (VECM) technique for determining the variables that are believed to generate inflation in Bangladesh. The present study differs from the study of Akhtaruzzaman in the sense that not to use the world price of tradable goods as an extra variable in our model rather the exchange rate, import price and the wider presentation of the related discussion in the ongoing study.

However, in case of most of the articles (except the work of Hossain and Akhtaruzzaman) estimations were done without examining the time series properties of the variables. The estimated regression results would be nonsense invalidating the t and F test in the presence of non-stationary variables.

Papers on unemployment are rarer especially from econometrics approach. Rahman, Matiuur, Mustafa, Muhammad, Islam, Anisul, Guru-Gharana, Kishor Kumar (2006) analyzed employment relating to the economic growth using multivariate cointegration methodology and vector error-correction models to investigate the factors that are likely to contribute to economic growth and employment in Bangladesh. Inflation or relation between inflation and unemployment is not highlighted here.

As far as our knowledge, no papers on inflation and unemployment attempt to make any relationship between this two. From this point of view, perhaps this article is the first effort trying to

see whether there exists any relation between inflation and unemployment and if yes, then how they look.

3. Data

The data set is annual, spanning 1973/74 through 2008/09. The dependent variable is the annualized inflation rate calculated using the Consumer Price Index (CPI General), and the explanatory variables are the annual GDP (real), import price index, and exchange rate. To test if the series are non-stationary or contain a unit root, we focus on the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) test. We have used EVIEWS 6 as statistical software package.

4. Modeling Inflation using Phillips Curve

Since official unemployment figures are hopelessly understood for Bangladesh, Phillips curve using unemployment is almost out of the question for Bangladesh. For deriving unemployment-gap Phillips curve model, it requires a strong consistent data series on unemployment, which is absent. What is left for the empirical modeler is an output-gap Phillips curve. The stylized version of the *expectation-augmented Phillips curve*, written in terms of output-gap, is typically assumed to be of the following form:

$$\pi_t = \pi_t^e - \gamma(y_t - y_t^*) + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Where π_t is the actual rate of inflation, π_t^e is the expected rate of inflation (expected at the beginning of period t), y_t is the actual level of output (or GDP), y_t^* is the potential output and the difference between two is the output gap and γ is the coefficient and ε_t is the error term.

If we use the triangle model of inflation then the Phillips curve may be re-written as:

$$\pi_t = \alpha_0 + \beta\pi_{t-1} + \gamma(y_t - y_t^*) + \phi z_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

Where α_0 the constant, inertia is represented by lags of inflation. And the output gap is defined as actual real (log) GDP minus potential GDP. As for supply shock variable z_t , we account exchange rate, and import price index simultaneously and estimate the above equation.

For Bangladesh, there seems to be a good *priori* reason for a backward-looking Phillips curve. In the present of serious data problem it is quiet impossible to establish a forward-looking Phillips curve for Bangladesh. For our backward-looking case, we use Equation [2].

5. Estimation

5.1. Econometric Methodology

Transforming all the variables into log forms, finally our baseline Phillips curve for Bangladesh is as follows which is just based on equation [2], the output-gap² Phillips curve:

$$LCPI = CONS + LEXCPI + LYGAP^* + LEXCH + LIMPORT + Ut \quad (3)$$

Where LCPI is the log of inflation

LEXCPI is the log of expected inflation³

LYGAP is the log of output gap⁴.

LEXCH and LIMPORT are the log of exchange rate and log of import price respectively as proxy for supply shock variable.

² There are several methods that can be used to construct the output gap term; all of which are contentious, and each has different strengths and drawbacks. It is not the purpose of this paper to study this issue in detail. For Bangladesh case the method which we have applied is explained briefly in Appendix 2.

³ The expected inflation for a backward looking Phillips curve is estimated using last period's inflation. (See Dua Puma)

⁴ For the purpose of testing output gap by Hodrick Prescott Filter Test, for smoothing parameter, λ is 100 for annual data.

5.2. Baseline Results

The equation was estimated as an OLS regression. The estimated coefficients of the baseline equation are reported in Table 2 in Appendix-2

All the estimated coefficients have expected sign. The coefficient on lagged inflation is positively correlated with the inflation rate meaning that current year inflation is influenced by the inflation previous years. A one-percentage point increase in the inflation rate in last year is associated with a 0.9352 percentage point increase in inflation this year when output gap is used. External price developments have been captured by exchange rate and import price index and exchange rate found to influence inflation. Import variable has negative sign. A one-percentage point increase of import is associated with a 0.9352 percentage point decrease in inflation. However, the size of the coefficient of import inflation is very small. Finally, R-Sq and R-Sq (adj) both show high values about fitting the models.

5.3. Unit Root Test

This analysis begins by pre-testing for order of integration of the series using both standard Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and the Phillips-Perron (PP) test. The null hypothesis of these tests is that series are non-stationary.

The ADF tests assume that the error terms are statistically independent and have a constant variance. This assumption may not be true of all the data used, and so the Phillip-Perron test is used to relax the above assumptions and permit the error disturbances to be heterogeneously distributed. In Appendix 3 table 3 and 4 present the results of the unit root tests both ADF and PP test for all series in levels and in respected differences respectively.

6. Johanson Jusilius Cointegratin Test

Since the integrated order of the variables is same, we can go for the cointegration test. The cointegration test results for all the variables are reported in Table: 5 located in Appendix 4. From the table it is seen that the null of cointegration among inflation and its determinants is rejected because for both Trace and Eigen values, the calculated values are greater than the critical values when $r = 0$ except the rest of the three cases. Thus, we can say that there is at least one cointegrating vector among inflation, output gap, exchange rate, and import price index.

7. Concluding Remarks

The estimation of the Phillips curve in Bangladesh is clearly characterized by the strong degree of the backward-looking dynamics of the inflation process. Inflation is negatively correlated with the output gap and lagged inflation and current inflation is positively correlated indicating previous year inflation causes inflation next year. We also find that the coefficients of output gap and import price inflation are also surprisingly small for such a small, open economy.

However, the whole result should be treated with some skepticism because the prior specification of the empirical equation of the Phillips curve is purely backward looking. Because there is a lack of data in the observations of inflation expectations as well as a consistent time series data on unemployment rate (for which estimating NAIRU becomes difficult), there is no scope for a formulation of the regression that allows for a direct effect of inflation expectation to show. The regression results suggest that inflation is BD is not caused by cost-push inflationary pressure but is aggregate demand, which causes inflation.

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Appendices

1. Appendix to Section 3: Data

This section lists the data and its sources-

Table 1: Variables in the inflation equation

Variable	Description	Source	Available from
π_t (LCPI)	Annual inflation rate (CPI)	BBS, Statistical Year Book and Economic Review	1976/77
π_t^e (LEXPTD)	Inflation expectations (est)	Constructed	-
Variable	Description	Source	Available from
$Y_t - Y_t^e$ (LYGAP)	Output gap (est)	Constructed	-
Y_t (Yt)	Annual GDP series (at current prices)	BBS, Statistical Year Book and Economic Review	1976/77
Z_{te} (LEXCHRT, LIM PRDX)	Exchange rate (Nominal), import price index	Statistical Year Book	1972/73
μ_t (URt)	Unemployment rate (est)	BBS, Statistical Year Book and ILO and some constructed	indefinite

2. Appendix to Section 5.2 Baseline Results

Table 2:

Variables	Dependent variable	Constant	LEXCPI	LYGAP	LEXCH	LIMPORT	R-Sq	R-Sq(adj)
EQ[3]	LCPI	0.0770 (0.82)	0.9352 (13.88*)	-0.0011 (-0.06**)	0.6977 (1.03**)	-0.018 (0.53**)	0.9932	0.99233

Notes: Dependent variable is inflation ($\Delta^2\pi_t$). t-Statistics are displayed in brackets.

* denotes rejection of H_0 at 1%, 5% and 10% level: the coefficient is zero

** denotes rejection of H_1 at 1%, 5% and 10% level: the coefficient is not equal to zero

Source: Authors' own calculation.

3. Appendix to Section 5.3 Unit Root Test

Table 3: Unit Root Test (NON-STATIONARITY)

Variables	Order of lag	ADF test statistics	PP test statistics
LCPI	1	-2.2679	-2.3050
LEXCPI	1	-2.9084	-4.0917
LYGAP	1	-2.9084	-4.0917
LEXCH	1	-3.6408	-2.4648
LIMPORT	1	-2.1239	-2.0070

Table 4: Unit root test (stationarity)

Variables	Order of integration	Order of lag	ADF test statistics	PP test statistics
LCPI	I(1)	1	-5.2734	-10.8539
LEXCPI	I(1)	1	-4.0905	-5.9338
LYGAP	I(1)	1	-6.2210	-9.5466
LEXCH	I(1)	1	-5.5640	-5.5427
LIMPORT	I(1)	1	-4.8673	-5.4174

4. Appendix to Section 6 Johanson Jusilius Test

Table 5: Johanson's Maximum Likelihood Results⁵(r = number of cointegrating vector) The Results of $\hat{\alpha}$ - Max and Trace Test for Phillips Curve Function

Null Alternative	$\hat{\alpha}$ -max* Statistics	95% critical values	Trace Statistics	95% critical values
r = 0 r =1	54.73448**	30.81507	85.22690**	55.24578
r <=1 r =2	14.66365	24.25202	30.49242	35.01090
r <=2 r =3	12.15891	17.14769	15.82876	18.39771
r <=3 r =4 3	669852	3.841466	3.669852	3.841466

* indicates the Max-Eigen value

** denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

5. Measuring Output Gap

In general, the different approaches to estimate potential output are classified into some of the detrending methods: the HP filter, the BP filter by Baxter-King, and the Kalman filter (univariate,

⁵ However, when we ran the test; the software did not give the result of expected inflation (LEXCPI).In others words, adding the variable expected inflation caused a problem in running the test. Therefore, we had no way but to run the test neglecting the variable expected inflation.

bivariate, and common permanent and cyclical components). For structural relationships approaches: the linear Time Trend method, SVAR method, and PF method .We have used linear Time Trend method to measure output-gap for Bangladesh. The linear trend method is the simplest way to estimate the output gap and potential output. According to this method, it is assumed that potential output is a deterministic function of time and the output gap is a residual from the trend line. It presumes that on average output is at its potential level over the sample period. Thus trend in output, which represents potential output, may be estimated as:

$$y_t^* = \hat{\alpha}_0 + \hat{\alpha}_1 \cdot Trend; t = 1, 2 \quad (1)$$

Where y_t^* is potential output and $\hat{\alpha}_i, i = 0, 1$ are the estimated coefficients from the regression of the actual output (y_t) on time trend variable and output gap (y_{gap_t}) is obtained by using

$$y_{gap_t} = y_t - y_t^* ; t = 1, 2 \quad (2)$$